

Relationships between structures and physical properties of PVDF/MWNT composite

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SUMMARY

Poly(vinylidene fluoride)(PVDF) / Multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWNT) composites were melt compounded. Structures and physical properties of PVDF/MWNT composite films were studied. The incorporation of MWNT produced a polar β -form crystal structure of PVDF. The permittivities, thermal/ electrical conductivities of thin PVDF/MWNT composite films were increased with increasing the MWNT content.

Keywords: Permittivity, Electrical conductivity, Poly(vinylidene fluoride)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In recent years, carbon nanotubes (CNTs)-reinforced polymer composites are attracting much attention due to their excellent electrical conductivity. The incorporation of CNTs with very high aspect ratio into the polymer matrix is expected to produce unique physical properties in comparison with those of composites with three-dimensional structured nanoparticle. Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) has been extensively studied because of its potential applications as piezoelectric and pyroelectric materials.

WAXD was used to observe the effect of MWNT content on the microstructure of thin PVDF composite films. Figure 1 describes the WAXD patterns for these composite films. Within a given range of scattering angles, three characteristic diffraction peaks appear at $2\theta = 17.7, 18.4,$ and 19.9° , which correspond to (100), (020), and (110) reflections, respectively. This is assigned to the α -phase crystal which has a non-polar trans-gauche-trans-gauche (TGTG) conformation. PVDF composites exhibit decreased peaks for α -phase crystal from 0.5 wt% content. In addition to the features associated with α -phase crystal, the introduction of MWNT produces a shoulder at a 2θ value of 20.7° and it is clearer with increasing the MWNT content. This is attributed to the formation of β -phase crystal, the most polar among other crystals. This exhibits

piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties of PVDF matrix.¹ We investigated the effect of MWNT content on the permittivity, electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity of PVDF. As shown in Figure 2, The permittivity of the PVDF composite was proportionally dependent on the content of MWNTs. Permittivity is improved with increasing the content of MWNT. However, permittivity is decreased with increasing the frequency in the range from 10^{-1} to 10^4 KHz. Ionic conduction phenomena are slightly observed above 5wt% of MWNT. These results implied obviously that the PVDF filled with MWNTs could be prospective EMI shield material since we can enhance the permittivity and conductivity by controlling the content of MWNT. Figure 3 shows the variation of the electrical conductivity of PVDF composites with the MWNT content (conductivity of MWNT : 75 S/cm, conductivity of PVDF : 10^{-14} S/cm). The electrical conductivity was increased from 10^{-14} to 10^0 S/cm with increasing the content of MWNT from 0 to 5wt%. However, when the content of MWNTs went over 5wt%, the electrical conductivity was almost independent of the MWNTs content. This indicates that there is conductivity saturation from a critical content because of formation of an infinite cluster.² Similar tendency was also observed in thermal conductivity above 3wt% of MWNT, as shown in Figure 4. In addition, the ferroelectric properties of PVDF composites will be discussed in this paper.

Figure 1. WAXD patterns of thin PVDF and PVDF/MWNT composite films.

Figure 2. Variation of the permittivity of thin PVDF and PVDF/MWNT composite films with MWNT content.

Figure 3. Variation of the electrical conductivity of thin PVDF and PVDF/MWNT composite films with MWNT content.

Figure 4. Variation of the thermal conductivity of thin PVDF and PVDF/MWNT composite films with MWNT content.

References

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